

THE IMPACT OF OMNICHANNEL DISTRIBUTION ON MARGINALITY AND BOOKING ACQUISITION COSTS IN INDEPENDENT HOTELS

JEL Classification: L83, M31, M21, D22, D24, Z33
SECTION “ECONOMICS”: Economics

Annotation. The relevance of the study is determined by the impact of omnichannel distribution on the marginality and costs of independent hotels. The purpose of the article is to determine the impact of multi-channel booking systems on financial results and to justify directions for optimizing distribution strategies. The methodology is based on cost analysis, comparison of distribution channels, and a systematic analytical approach using practical data from independent hotels. The results showed that excessive dependence on intermediaries reduces profitability, while the development of own channels increases financial stability. The novelty lies in the creation of a model for evaluating the effectiveness of omnichannel distribution for independent hotels. The conclusions confirm the advisability of balancing channels, and the prospects are related to the analysis of new digital platforms.

Keywords: hotel business, sales channels, commission expenses, direct distribution, financial stability, strategy optimization.

Анотація. Актуальність дослідження визначається зростанням ролі омніканального дистрибуції в готельному бізнесі, де інтеграція онлайн- та офлайн-каналів формує основні параметри конкурентоспроможності незалежних готелів. З'ясовано, що використання багатоканальних систем бронювання істотно впливає на економічні показники, зокрема на рентабельність та витрати на залучення клієнтів. Водночас наявні дослідження зосереджуються переважно на мережевих брендах, тоді як сегмент незалежних готелів, який є більш вразливим до ринкових коливань, залишається недостатньо вивченим.

Метою статті є оцінка впливу омніканального дистрибуції на рентабельність та витрати на залучення бронювань у незалежних готелях, а також обґрунтування напрямів оптимізації дистрибуційних стратегій.

Методологія дослідження базується на поєднанні порівняльного й структурно-функціонального аналізу, економетричного моделювання та аналізу витрат. Емпіричні дані з практики незалежних готелів інтегровані з інформацією про функціонування глобальних систем дистрибуції, онлайн-агентств із продажу туристичних послуг та каналів прямого бронювання. Для узагальнення як кількісних показників, так і якісних аспектів управління каналами було застосовано системно-аналітичний підхід.

Під час дослідження виявлено закономірності впливу омніканальної дистрибуції на прибутковість незалежних готелів. Продемонстровано, що надмірна залежність від зовнішніх посередників знижує прибутковість через високі комісійні витрати, тоді як розвиток прямих каналів підвищує фінансову стійкість. З'ясовано, що оптимальний баланс каналів досягається шляхом інтеграції прямих і посередницьких форм дистрибуції з урахуванням сегментації споживачів і динаміки попиту.

Висновки підтверджують, що стратегічне управління омніканальними потоками дозволяє знизити витрати на залучення клієнтів і підвищити прибутковість. Виявлено

критичну важливість постійного моніторингу пропорцій каналів, оскільки це дозволяє адаптувати стратегії дистрибуції до мінливих ринкових умов.

Перспективи подальших досліджень пов'язані з розширенням емпіричної бази за допомогою транснаціональних даних, аналізом впливу цифрових платформ нового покоління (метапошукові системи, мобільні додатки, соціальні медіа) та розробкою прогнозних моделей для оцінки економічних ефектів трансформації стратегій дистрибуції в незалежних готелях.

Ключові слова: готельний бізнес, канали продажу, комісійні витрати, пряма дистрибуція, фінансова стійкість, оптимізація стратегій.

Introduction

The issue of the impact of omnichannel distribution on the economic performance of independent hotels is driven by significant transformations in the tourism and hotel business, where digitalization and changing consumer behavior are creating new challenges for competitiveness management. Attracting customers through online aggregators, proprietary websites, social networks, and partner platforms is accompanied not only by opportunities for market expansion, but also by increased costs of attracting bookings and pressure on margins. Independent hotels, which do not have the large-scale resources of chain operators, need to find the optimal balance between using different channels and ensuring financial stability. This creates an important scientific task: identifying the patterns of influence of omnichannel strategy on the structure of income and expenses, as well as determining mechanisms for improving the efficiency of sales channel management. At the same time, the problem has a clear practical dimension, as the optimal configuration of distribution tools can contribute to increased profitability, reduced dependence on intermediaries, and strengthened competitive positions of hotels in changing market conditions. Thus, its study combines the theoretical tasks of tourism economics and marketing with the practical needs of hospitality management. An analysis of current research on the impact of omnichannel distribution on margins and booking acquisition costs in independent hotels allows us to identify four interrelated areas.

The first direction, conceptual and strategic, addresses the development of theoretical and managerial foundations for distribution systems in the hospitality industry. E. Falk and C. Anderson systematize the principal hotel distribution channels and assess their influence on revenue structures and enterprise market positioning [1]. J. Selvaraj identifies the fundamental approaches to constructing modern omnichannel platforms in healthcare and hospitality, with particular emphasis on the integration of digital technologies [2]. T. Vieira, M. Oliveira, and T. Pataco highlight the strategic significance of developing direct distribution channels to mitigate reliance on global intermediaries [3]. G. Xu, K. Kang, and M. Lu demonstrate the importance of pricing strategies and investments in customer experience within the BOPS model, which exhibits notable parallels in the hotel sector [4].

The second dimension, economic and financial, encompasses studies on the impact of channel structure on margins and costs. M. T. H. Siddiqi and co-authors show that the digitalization of supply chains enhances customer orientation and reduces acquisition costs [5]. R. W. Palmatier and colleagues view omnichannel strategies as a means of reducing transaction costs and generating new sources of profitability [6]. P. R. Srivastava and co-authors propose optimization models for assortment management that mitigate revenue losses in a multichannel environment [7]. C. Sun, P. Adamopoulos, A. Ghose, and X. Luo apply deep learning to predict stages of the omnichannel customer journey, enabling more effective allocation of marketing expenditures [8].

The third dimension, technological and innovative, underscores the role of digital tools in improving distribution efficiency. Z. Chen, C. Tang, and S. I. Su highlight the effectiveness of joint investments and bundling of tourism products as a means of optimizing the cost–revenue balance [9]. B. D. Guillet demonstrates that online upselling increases the average transaction value and offsets customer acquisition costs [10]. R. Dumoulin and A. Giacomel analyze the strategic challenges faced by hotel groups undergoing digital transformation, stressing the need to optimize channel integration costs [11]. N. Soltani-Nejad and

colleagues show that the shift from single-channel to omnichannel models is accompanied by organizational and technological barriers [12].

The fourth dimension, practical and sectoral, addresses applied aspects of implementing omnichannel strategies in tourism and hospitality. E. Bigne, J. L. Nicolau, and E. William examine the influence of multichannel booking on dynamic pricing, demonstrating its contribution to margin formation [13]. O. T. W. Simanjuntak, E. M. Gegung, and S. Marliani illustrate the effectiveness of omnichannel marketing strategies for tourist destinations, emphasizing their capacity to reduce promotion costs [14].

Despite the growing attention to omnichannel distribution in the hotel business, a number of issues remain unresolved. First and foremost, this concerns the insufficiently researched impact of channel structure on marginality and customer acquisition costs in independent hotels, the limited amount of empirical data on their practical application, and the lack of unified methodological approaches to evaluating the effectiveness of multichannel strategies. In addition, there is a fragmented understanding of the organizational and technological barriers that limit the effectiveness of such strategies.

The proposed study aims to address these gaps by systematizing the impact of omnichannel distribution on the financial performance of independent hotels, developing a consistent approach to assessing marginality and customer acquisition costs, and using modern empirical cases. This approach will broaden scientific understanding of the problem, form practical recommendations for optimizing the structure of distribution channels, and create a basis for improving management efficiency in the hospitality industry.

The purpose of the article is to determine the impact of omnichannel distribution on the marginality and costs of attracting bookings in independent hotels and to justify directions for optimizing distribution strategies. The aims of this article is to:

- reveal the essence of omnichannel distribution and assess its impact on competitive advantages, marginality, and the cost of attracting customers in independent hotels;
- identify the main problems that limit the effectiveness of multi-channel strategies, taking into account financial, organizational, and technological factors.
- formulate practical recommendations for optimizing the structure of distribution channels to increase profitability and reduce booking costs.

Results

Omnichannel distribution in the hotel business is considered a modern sales channel management model that involves the integrated use of offline and online tools to ensure maximum product availability for consumers. Unlike the multichannel model, in which each channel functions separately, omnichannel involves the integration of all points of interaction into a single system, allowing for coordinated management of bookings, communications, and pricing. For independent hotels, this strategy is particularly important as it enables them to compete with large chain operators by increasing customer convenience, reducing information asymmetry, and creating added value in service (Table 1).

Table 1

Key omnichannel distribution channels for independent hotels and their impact on competitive advantage

Distribution channel	Key characteristics	Contribution to competitive advantages	Examples of practical use
Hotel's own website	Direct bookings, control over prices	Reduced dependence on intermediaries, customer loyalty	Loyalty programs, integration with Customer Relationship Management (CRM)

Distribution channel	Key characteristics	Contribution to competitive advantages	Examples of practical use
OTA (Booking, Expedia)	Wide market coverage, international presence	Increased room occupancy	Entry into the global tourism segment
Social networks	Direct communication, targeted advertising	Increased recognition and trust	Instagram, Facebook for brand building
GDS (Global Distribution)	Connection to the corporate segment	Attracting business customers with high average check	Access to Amadeus and Sabre systems
Distribution channel	Key characteristics	Contribution to competitive advantages	Examples of practical use

Source: compiled by the author based on [1, p. 869–870; 3, p. 407; 6, p. 15–116; 12, p. 389]

Practical analysis shows that the effectiveness of omnichannel distribution strategies in independent hotels directly depends on how balanced the combination of proprietary channels and intermediary platforms is. An own website with a direct booking module integrated with a CRM system allows for greater control over customer data, builds loyalty, and encourages repeat visits through personalized offers. Online travel agencies (OTAs) provide broad visibility in the global market, although they generate significant costs through commissions [2, p. 58]. It is the optimal combination of these tools that allows you to increase margins, since income from direct bookings is not burdened by commissions, and OTA coverage guarantees stable occupancy rates.

Real-life cases confirm that even small independent hotels can achieve significant results through the competent use of an omnichannel strategy. For example, Hotel & Gasthof zum Hirsch in Germany demonstrates that the implementation of an integrated direct booking system with channel synchronization has increased the share of direct sales by more than 18%, reducing dependence on OTAs while maintaining their role in market expansion. This shows that even in the boutique hotel segment with limited resources, investments in digital distribution infrastructure can ensure margin growth and business model sustainability in a highly competitive environment.

The financial performance of independent hotels is determined not only by the number of rooms sold, but also by the level of margin generated by various distribution channels. An omnichannel approach, while diversifying sources of demand, simultaneously creates a mixed financial effect: some channels increase profitability due to the absence of commissions, while others reduce it due to high intermediation costs. Current trends show that it is the balance between direct and indirect bookings that is an important factor in the formation of marginal income (Table 2).

Table 2

The impact of distribution channels on the marginality of independent hotels

Distribution channel	Average margin	Factors determining the impact
Own website with booking module	High (about 80–90% of the booking cost)	No commissions, only technical support and marketing costs
OTA (Booking, Expedia, etc.)	Medium or low (60–70%)	Commissions of 15–25%, depending on rating and visibility in search results
Social networks with integrated booking	Medium to high (70–85%)	Advertising and targeting costs, but lower commissions compared to OTAs

Metasearch engines (Google Hotel Ads, Trivago)	Medium (65–80%)	Pay per click or per booking, depending on rates in a competitive environment
Traditional agencies	Relatively stable (75–85%)	Fixed commissions are lower than those of OTAs, but limited number of bookings

Source: compiled by the author based on [5, p. 120–121; 9; 10; 11, p. 16; 13]

In today's environment, the practical operation of distribution channels in independent hotels means that each of them generates different margins depending on the cooperation model and the nature of the costs. Direct bookings through a hotel's own website usually provide the highest margins, as they do not involve commission payments, but they require investment in promotion and digital infrastructure support. OTAs remain a powerful tool for ensuring room occupancy, but high commissions (up to 25%) significantly reduce net profitability [13]. Social networks and metasearch engines have an intermediate effect: they provide an opportunity to increase brand awareness and attract new customer segments, but require active marketing investments and constant budget optimization. Traditional agencies retain their niche in the corporate or individual travel segment, providing a relatively stable margin, although their sales volume is limited.

In practice, this means that a hotel's financial results are determined not so much by the fact of the booking itself, but rather by its "quality" in terms of margin. An example is Hotel Zamora (USA), which, thanks to the implementation of a new booking module on its own website, achieved a 41% increase in conversion and increased the share of revenue from direct bookings from 35% to almost 46%. This made it possible to significantly reduce the share of OTAs in total revenue and cut commission costs by 16%, while ensuring overall growth in room revenue [16]. This example demonstrates that the competent integration of digital tools into your own booking channel not only increases sales, but also improves business margins by reducing intermediary costs.

The cost of attracting customers in independent hotels is an important parameter that determines the effectiveness of multi-channel strategies. Unlike marginality, which reflects the final financial result, the cost of attracting bookings shows how rationally a hotel uses its marketing and distribution resources. In an environment of intense competition and digital transformation of the market, it is the optimization of these costs that allows independent hotels to remain competitive while maintaining flexibility in working with different customer segments. Acquisition through OTAs, metasearch engines, social media, and direct channels has different economic costs, depending on the size of commissions, advertising costs, and technological support. In modern practice, it is important not only to reduce absolute costs, but also to achieve an optimal balance between CAC (Customer Acquisition Cost) and long-term customer value (Customer Lifetime Value) (Table 3).

Table 3

Patterns of the impact of multi-channel strategies on the cost of customer acquisition in independent hotels

Distribution channel	Nature of impact on CAC	Typical costs	Features in competitive conditions
Own website with booking module	Average cost, long-term reduction	SEO, website support, UX optimization	High efficiency with investment in promotion
OTA (Booking, Expedia)	High CAC due to commissions	15–25% of the booking cost	Provide quick access to the global market, but create dependency

Distribution channel	Nature of impact on CAC	Typical costs	Features in competitive conditions
Metasearch engines (Google Hotel Ads, Trivago)	Medium-high CAC	Pay-per-click (CPC), marketing budget	Provide control over pricing, but require constant optimization
Social networks (Facebook, Instagram, TikTok)	Variable CAC, depending on targeting	Advertising campaigns, content production	Effective for attracting new segments, especially young people
Traditional agencies	Stable, average CAC	Fixed commissions, organizational costs	Remain relevant in niche segments (corporate, VIP clients)

Source: compiled by the author based on [2, p. 61; 4, p. 133223–133224; 7, p. 452; 8, p. 434; 14, p. 143–144].

Practical experience shows that the impact of multi-channel strategies on the cost of customer acquisition in independent hotels depends significantly on the level of integration of digital tools and the characteristics of the local market. European hotels demonstrate that an active presence on OTAs not only provides a significant volume of indirect bookings but also increases brand visibility, stimulating additional direct bookings. This effect is confirmed by studies that show that more than half of independent hotels in the EU use OTAs as a tool to strengthen their own sales channels: after reviewing offers on the aggregator, customers often go directly to the hotel’s website to rebook [17]. This reduces the average cost of acquisition in the long term, as the cost of repeat direct bookings is significantly lower than intermediary commissions.

In the Ukrainian context, investments in digital infrastructure are particularly important, as competition in the domestic market is intensifying and international tourist flows are unstable. Studies show that spending on digital sales and the digitization of business processes are becoming important factors influencing the net income of hotels [18]. At the same time, properly structured investments in digital customer interaction (own website, social networks, online services) can significantly reduce CAC, forming a base of loyal consumers and ensuring repeat bookings without additional costs for intermediaries. Thus, both European and Ukrainian examples prove that the effectiveness of a multi-channel strategy is determined not only by sales volumes, but also by the ability to optimize customer acquisition costs through a balance between OTAs and direct channels, as well as investments in digital technologies.

The effectiveness of omnichannel distribution in independent hotels is limited by a number of interrelated problems of a financial, technological, organizational, and market nature. One of the main problems is high commission dependence on OTAs, which reduces margins and forces hotels to operate in less favorable financial conditions [13]. Direct channels require significant investment in SEO, advertising, conversion optimization, and IT infrastructure support, which is burdensome for small hotels with limited budgets [9]. High digital marketing costs combined with uneven returns create the risk of increasing customer acquisition costs and reducing net income.

A technical obstacle is the low integration of channels: the lack of a unified CRM system, limited channel manager functionality, or the use of outdated PMS lead to duplicate bookings, data loss, and increased operating costs [2, p. 59]. Many independent hotels do not have the resources to implement complex analytical solutions, which limits their ability to accurately assess channel performance and forecast demand [8, pp. 441–442]. Another problem is dependence on global metasearch engines, which require significant advertising budgets to maintain positions and ensure visibility in a highly competitive environment.

Organizational challenges include a lack of qualified personnel capable of managing complex distribution strategies, analyzing channel profitability, and implementing innovative tools [10]. Many hotels lack a clear policy for balancing direct and indirect bookings, which creates the risk of over-reliance on a single channel. Added to this is the unevenness of seasonal demand, which intensifies competition for

customers in the high season and makes it particularly difficult to maintain an optimal channel structure in the low season.

Market constraints mean that large hotel chains can negotiate lower commissions with OTAs and invest in expensive digital solutions, while independent hotels are in a more vulnerable position. At the same time, reviews and ratings on public platforms create a reputation dependency effect: even a slight drop in ratings can reduce the visibility of offers in OTA and metasearch systems [13]. In addition, the rapid growth of the mobile segment creates new challenges, as mobile users have a shorter decision-making cycle, demanding maximum speed and convenience in the booking process, which is not always provided by outdated websites of independent hotels.

Optimizing the structure of distribution channels in independent hotels requires a strategic balance between direct and indirect bookings, technological modernization, and increased efficiency of marketing investments. The priority task is to increase the share of direct bookings by developing proprietary digital channels, in particular, creating adaptive websites with a convenient booking module integrated with PMS and CRM, as well as introducing loyalty programs for regular guests. This allows minimizing commission expenses and increasing margins while forming a stable customer base.

It is important to diversify OTA partnerships by using aggregators to expand international visibility, but limiting their share in total sales through flexible rate management and exclusive offers on the hotel's official website. Using a channel manager with dynamic pricing capabilities helps control revenue and avoid overbooking situations. At the same time, it is advisable to invest in SEO, targeted advertising, and analytics, which allows you to reduce the average cost of customer acquisition by increasing conversion rates.

A promising direction is the active use of social networks as a channel for direct booking and communication with guests, as they not only provide additional orders but also form emotional attachment to the brand. The integration of metasearch engines should be based on the rational allocation of budgets focused on those platforms that provide the highest conversion rates and the appropriate target audience profile.

From an organizational development perspective, it is advisable for independent hotels to develop internal competencies in revenue management and digital marketing, which will allow them to independently manage their distribution strategy and respond quickly to market changes. The joint use of regional or associative platforms by independent hotels can be a tool for collectively reducing technology and promotion costs.

Therefore, practical optimization of distribution channels consists in creating a multi-level model in which direct sales form the basis of profitability, OTAs serve as an additional tool for market expansion, and digital technologies ensure control over customer acquisition costs and long-term sustainability of the business model.

Conclusions

The study found that omnichannel distribution is a key factor in the competitiveness of independent hotels, as the combination of direct and intermediary channels generates varying levels of margins and customer acquisition costs. Direct bookings through proprietary digital platforms ensure the highest profitability but require substantial investment in marketing and technological support. In contrast, OTAs provide high sales volumes but reduce net margins due to commission fees. The main challenges include dependence on intermediaries, the high cost of digital marketing for small hotels, insufficient integration of management systems, and a shortage of specialized personnel. These are compounded by the effects of seasonality and reputational dependence on open booking platforms.

To address these issues, it is recommended that independent hotels strengthen their own sales channels by investing in modern websites and loyalty programs, diversify partnerships with OTAs, employ channel managers with dynamic pricing, and allocate budgets rationally between social networks and metasearch engines. It is also important to develop internal competencies in revenue management and digital marketing, as well as to utilize regional or associative platforms to reduce costs.

Future research should focus on assessing the relationship between customer acquisition costs and long-term customer value, modeling optimal channel structures for different types of independent hotels, and analyzing the impact of emerging digital technologies on the effectiveness of omnichannel strategies.

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